

Evaluation Report on the Hybrid Training Event 2025

Research Data Management Training for NFDI Consortia

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Introduction

During the Initialisation phase of the RDMTraining4NFDI project, the project team organized a training event on Research Data Management (RDM) for data stewards and RDM multipliers within the NFDI. Since the originally planned summer school and online workshop series did not align with the current needs of the community, RDMTraining4NFDI decided to organize a hybrid event, with insights from experienced external trainers.

This hybrid event was designed for both beginners and experienced professionals in RDM who were already providing or planning to provide generic and/or discipline-specific training. The programme offered a dynamic mix of learning formats. Where possible, parallel sessions were tailored to different experience levels. Participants had the flexibility to register for one, several, or all event formats, depending on their interests and availability.

The hybrid event aimed to:

1. Deliver practical, focused RDM guidance within a condensed time frame (six weeks)
2. Strengthen participants' training skills and data management expertise
3. Foster the exchange of good practices within the RDM community
4. Experiment with and evaluate diverse training formats

It ran from October 28th to December 11th 2025, starting with an in-person kick-off event on Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management on October 28th and 29th 2025. The programme continued, in parallel, with an online interactive workshop series (six three-hour workshops in total) and six self-learning modules from November 3rd to 21st 2025 (guide¹, authors: Justine Vandendorpe, Marco Uebachs). This was followed by an asynchronous homework phase², during which participants adapted RDM training materials by choosing preferred topics from the hybrid event programme for their specific disciplines (November 24th to December 5th 2025). The event concluded with a two-hour online wrap-up session on December 11th 2025, where participants presented their homework results and took part in a focus group discussion as part of the evaluation. A companion event pad³ was used to keep participants informed and communicate with them throughout the event. An overview of dates, formats, locations, topics, trainers/authors, and materials is provided in table 1.

Table 1. Overview of the hybrid event, including the date, format, number of participants, topic, trainer(s)/author(s), and link(s) to each individual event/module.

Date	Format	No.*	Topic	Trainer / Author	Link
2025-10-28 -	Onsite Lunch-to-lu	13	Strategic Data Stewardship &	Antje Manske	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14221846

¹ Guide to support participants of the RDMT4NFDI Hybrid Event during the self-learning modules: https://iascript.github.io/course/?https://raw.githubusercontent.com/MUebachs/RDMTraining4NFDI_Hybrid-Event-Research_Data_Management_for-NFDI_Consortia/refs/heads/main/README.md#1

² Vandendorpe, J., Manske, A., Wohltmann, M., & Uebachs, M. (2026). From Learning to Practice — Tailoring RDM Training Materials to Your Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18935544>

³ History of the companion event pad: <https://cryptpad.fr/pad/#/2/pad/view/3RLLD4BHG0u4tY32glhvTID2O5EZqM6WwM9e9KNBqN0/>

Date	Format	No.*	Topic	Trainer / Author	Link
2025-10-29	nch kick-off event		Change Management		
2025-11-04	Online workshop	11	Foundations of RDM for Beginners	Justine Vandendorpe, Sophie Boße	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17588631
2025-11-06	Online workshop	8	Practical Data Protection in Research	Neelam Vishen	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17588748
2025-11-11	Online workshop	8	Python for Beginners	Justine Vandendorpe, Rabea Müller	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422255
2025-11-11	Online workshop	6	Python for Beginners	Justine Vandendorpe, Rabea Müller	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422341
2025-11-13	Online workshop	7	Git for Beginners	Rabea Müller	https://librarycarpentry.github.io/lc-git/02-getting-started.html
2025-11-13	Online workshop	3	Git for Advanced	Till Sauerwein	https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/hifis/software/education/hifis-workshops/software-development-for-teams/workshop-materials
2025-11-18	Online workshop	8	Introduction to Galaxy	Daniela Schneider, Armin Dadras, Björn Grüning	https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/introduction/tutorials/galaxy-intro-101-everyone/tutorial.html
2025-11-20	Online workshop	11	Didactics & Motivation	Mareike Wohltmann, Rabea Müller	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17701667
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Foundations of RDM for Advanced	Katarzyna Biernacka et al.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13927614
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Open Science	The Turing Way Community	https://book.the-turing-way.org/reproducible-research/open
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Python for Advanced		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422640
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Python for Advanced		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422650

Date	Format	No.*	Topic	Trainer / Author	Link
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Python for Advanced		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422702
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Python for Advanced		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422806
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Git for Beginners	Silvia di Giorgio et al.	https://librarycarpentry.github.io/lc-git/02-getting-started.html
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Train-the-Trainer Workshop on Data Management Plans (DMPs)	Marisabel Gonzalez-Ocañto	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771035
2025-11-03 - 2025-11-21	Self-learning modules	NA	Sharing Data & Metadata	Vanessa Gabriel et al.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16792998
2025-11-24 - 2025-12-05	Asynchronous homework phase	NA	From Learning to Practice : Tailoring RDM Training Materials to Your Community	Justine Vandendorpe	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18935544
2025-12-11	Online Wrap-up event	5	Participants' homework results and focus group discussion	Justine Vandendorpe, Mareike Wohltmann	NA

*No.= number of participants

Methods

For the evaluation of the hybrid event and its different modules, we adopted various approaches which are described below.

We conducted a survey after the in-person kick-off event and online interactive workshop series via 2ask⁴, focusing primarily on evaluating the content of the training and satisfaction levels. For this survey a 5-Point Likert Scale was used. To measure the participants' subjective assessments of their acquired skills, self-confidence, and knowledge, we adopted a survey from the Carpentries⁵ using a 7-Point Likert Scale before and after the Python

⁴ provided by orbiz Software GmbH, Robert-Gerwig-Str. 4, 78467 Konstanz. The collected data was handled in accordance with GDPR and was not transferred outside Germany.

⁵ <https://carpentries.org/>

workshop and at a second post-test conducted one to two weeks later. The survey questions are published with the report for detailed information.

We analysed the data in Python (Version 3.12.3). The data and code are published with the report, whereby the details of the analysis methods are accessible.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the format, we used qualitative approaches: three interviews with participants and one interview with two experts. The interviews were conducted in German via Zoom (Version 6.3.6) by the RDMTraining4NFDI project manager and transcribed by two team members who were not involved in the interview (Cryptpad). The source data is unstructured (text).

We conducted semi-structured interviews with three participants who were registered in all formats (in-person kick-off event, online interactive workshop series, self-learning modules, asynchronous homework phase). Participants were chosen based on the characteristics of different consortia and different knowledge levels in RDM training to get a broad overview (purposive sampling). The objectives of these interviews were the identification of positive and negative learning experiences in relation to the different training formats, the analysis of participants' perceptions regarding the perceived impact of the various training formats and the provision of insights and recommendations for conducting training courses on RDM.

The data were analysed by using the thematic approach by Braun & Clarke, 2006. The analyses were conducted and written in German and then translated into English by using DeepL Translate (Version 25.8.2).

To evaluate the self-learning format, a semi-structured expert interview was conducted. Two RDM experts were asked for their feedback on the self-learning format. The interview focused thematically on the didactic design and content of the self-learning module. The transcript was evaluated using MaxQDA (version 26.0.0). First, the interviews were coded and then the codes were thematically clustered in order to provide assistance in the subsequent evaluation of the interview results. The analyses were conducted in German and written in English.

Further, we conducted two discussions: one discussion in order to evaluate the asynchronous homework phase and one discussion in order to evaluate the hybrid event in total (focus group discussion). During the wrap-up event, we discussed with two participants who had used the homework guide⁶ to adapt RDM training materials to their discipline about their satisfaction and the effectiveness of this format. We took notes during the meeting and summarised them using AI tools (MAXQDA Tailwind⁷) to reduce subjectivity. The summary was reviewed and adapted by the authors where needed. This method was also used for the focus group discussion.

Results

The following section presents the results of the survey from the onsite and online modules of the hybrid event, the qualitative interviews (experts interview on the self-learning format and semi-structured interviews with participants of all four formats), the discussion about the asynchronous homework format and the focus group discussion.

⁶ Vandendorpe, J., Manske, A., Wohltmann, M., & Uebachs, M. (2026). From Learning to Practice — Tailoring RDM Training Materials to Your Community. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18935544>

⁷ MAXQDA Tailwind: <https://tailwind.maxqda.com/>

Survey

Figure 1. Suitability Ratings by Module

Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management (n = 9)

This training had a high suitability (>78 %) for all items, with full suitability in the content (**Fig. 1**).

Foundations of RDM for Beginners (n = 10)

Foundations of RDM for Beginners was highly suitable in terms of content, difficulty of exercises, number of exercises and level of participation. New information had a suitability rating of only 60 % (**Fig. 1**), which indicates the high knowledge level of RDM multipliers in this event, since participants assessed this item in the majority as too low (**Tab. 2**).

Practical Data Protection in Research (n = 7)

This training showed full suitability regarding content and number of exercises, and high suitability in new information (86 %) and a suitability of 71 % for difficulty of exercises and 57% for level of participation (**Fig. 1**).

Python for Beginners (n = 6)

This training reached a high suitability (>82 %) for all items except new information (50 %) (**Fig. 1**).

Git for Advanced (n = 3)

The training module was assessed as fully suitable in terms of the number of exercises and the level of participation. The content and the amount of new information were rated as suitable by two of the three participants (67%) (**Fig. 1**). Two of the three participants assessed the difficulty of the exercises to be somewhat too low (**Tab. 2**).

Git for Beginners (n = 5)

The number of exercises and difficulty of exercises resulted in a high suitability of 80 %, whereas the level of participation was lower (60 %), and the content and new information of the training indicated suitability of 40 % among participants (**Fig. 1**). One participant responded only to the item on content in this section of the survey (**Tab. 2**). This response was still included in the analysis.

Introduction to Galaxy (n = 8)

The training showed a high suitability of over 88% across all factors except for the difficulty of the exercises (62%) (**Fig. 1**), which 38% of the participants rated as somewhat too low (**Tab. 2**).

Didactics & Motivation (n = 6)

The number of exercises was fully suitable and the difficulty of the exercises reached a high level in suitability with 87 %, whereas the content, new information and level of participation were lower at 67 % (**Fig. 1**).

Table 2: Suitability of content, new information, level of difficulty, number of exercises and level of participation per participant

Modules	Suitability of*				
	<i>the amount of content</i>	<i>the amount of new information</i>	<i>the level of difficulty of the exercises</i>	<i>the number of exercises</i>	<i>the level of participation</i>
Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management (n = 9)	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Too high
					Somewhat too low
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable		Somewhat too low	Somewhat too low	
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Somewhat too low	
	Suitable	too low	too low	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
Foundations of RDM for beginners	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable

(n = 10)	Suitable	Suitable Somewhat	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	too low	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable Somewhat too low	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	too low Somewhat	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable Somewhat too high	too low Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable Somewhat too low
Practical Data Protection in Research (n = 7)	Suitable	Somewhat too high	Suitable	Suitable	Somewhat too high Somewhat too low
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	too low
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Suitable	Somewhat too low
Python for Beginners (n = 6)	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable Somewhat too low
	Suitable Somewhat too high	Suitable Somewhat too high	Suitable	Suitable	too low
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Somewhat too low	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	too low	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
Git for Advanced (n = 3)	Suitable	Somewhat too low	Somewhat too low	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable Somewhat too low	Suitable	too low	Suitable	Suitable
	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
Git for Beginners (n = 5)	Somewhat too high				

	Suitable Somewhat too low	Suitable Somewhat too high	Suitable Somewhat too high	Suitable Somewhat too high	Suitable Somewhat too low
Introduction to Galaxy (n = 8)	Suitable Suitable	Suitable Suitable	Suitable Suitable Somewhat too low	Suitable Suitable Somewhat too high	Suitable Suitable Somewhat too high
	Suitable Somewhat too low	Suitable Suitable	Suitable Somewhat too low	Suitable Suitable	Suitable Suitable
Didactics & Motivation (n = 6)	Suitable Somewhat too low Somewhat too high	Suitable Somewhat too low Suitable	Suitable Somewhat too low Suitable	Suitable Suitable Suitable	Suitable Somewhat too low Suitable Somewhat too high

*5-Point Likert Scale: too low, somewhat too low, suitable, somewhat too high, too high

Level of helpfulness, confidence and satisfaction

Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management, Practical Data Protection in Research, Git for Advanced, and Didactics & Motivation were rated as helpful, whereas the mean for the remaining modules ranged between neutral and helpful.

For the modules Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management, Foundations of RDM for Beginners, Git for Advanced, and Didactics & Motivation, participants reported being confident in applying the knowledge. For the remaining modules, mean ranged between neutral and confident, except for Git for Beginners.

Overall, participants were satisfied with the modules, except for Git for Beginners and Introduction to Galaxy, where the mean ratings were between neutral and satisfied. However, for Introduction to Galaxy, five participants rated it as satisfied, one as very satisfied, one as dissatisfied, and one as very dissatisfied, resulting in a mean of 3.50 (Tab. 3).

Table 3: Level of helpfulness, confidences and satisfaction

Module	<i>Helpfulness*</i>		<i>Confidence*</i>		<i>Satisfaction*</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management (n = 9)	4.11	0.60	4.00	0.00	4.56	0.53
Foundations of RDM for beginners (n = 10)	3.90	0.32	4.30	0.48	4.00	0.67
Practical Data Protection in Research (n = 7)	4.14	0.69	3.57	0.53	4.14	0.38
Python for Beginners (n = 6)	3.67	0.82	3.67	0.52	4.00	0.89
Git for Advanced (n = 3)	4.33	0.58	4.33	0.58	4.67	0.58
Git for Beginners (n = 5)	3.40	0.89	2.20	1.79	3.60	0.89
Introduction to Galaxy (n = 8)	3.75	0.71	3.75	0.71	3.50	1.31
Didactics & Motivation (n = 6)	4.00	0.89	4.00	0.63	4.00	0.63

*5-Point Likert Scale

Pre- and post survey Python for Beginners

The participants' (n = 6) subjective assessments of their acquired skills, self-confidence, and knowledge, measured using a 7-point Likert scale before and after the Python workshop, indicated a slight overall increase after the workshop and at a second post-test conducted one to two weeks later.

Experts interview on self-learning format⁸

Didactic quality of self-designed self-learning material:

⁸ Vandendorpe, J., Schmitz, J., Manske, A., Uebachs, M., Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Sauerwein, T., Wohltmann, M. (2025). RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event: Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia. Liascript. Version 1.0. https://github.com/MUebachs/RDMTraining4NFDI_Hybrid-Event-Research_Data_Management_for-NFDI_Consortia/tree/main

When designing self-learning materials, both interviewed experts ensure that the purpose of the learning material can be quickly understood in terms of didactic aspects. One expert primarily anticipates possible questions from the target group and strives to identify problematic areas where an exercise could become an issue. The other expert emphasises the importance of clearly defining the learning objectives: What are the overall and individual goals? What should the learner be able to do at the end? And how can this be achieved with the planned concept?

Both experts agreed that the material should be variety-rich in structure. They aim for a balance between input and output, practice and instruction, avoid overly long texts, and ensure that the learning materials include interactive elements. They also recommend varying the formats (e.g., videos, podcasts, text) to appeal to different learning abilities.

When designing self-learning materials, both interviewees focus on the learning objectives. The accuracy of the content was also mentioned.

Assessment of the suitability of formats and didactic quality of the materials:

One expert found the self-learning material on Git for Beginners very variety-rich, but at the same time identified a gap between the learning level for beginners, which the course promised to be, and the skills it required. The experts question whether this Git module is suitable as a topic for a self-learning unit. In their opinion there is a lack of assistance where learners can ask for help if something within the tool does not work.

One respondent criticised the lack of consistency in some of the self-learning materials and the fact that there was no comparison with the learning objectives. As a result, it was not fully clear whether the person could do it in the end. There was criticism of the didactics with regards to consistency on the topic of 'open science'. Specifically, one slide ("Sharing Data") was noted as not comprehensible at all.

Both experts rated the Data Management Plan (DMP) Train the Trainer format, which was designed specially for this event and audience, as very good from a didactic point of view. This module fully meets the quality for self-learning from a didactic perspective.

When asked to what extent the self-learning materials are suitable for self-directed learning, one expert recommended that tool-related learning opportunities be removed from the self-learning modules and rather conducted in-person. This module on Git for Beginners should not be offered in a self-learning format, while the self-learning format for Git for Advanced could still be open to discussion. The other expert also saw opportunities for in-depth learning for this topic.

Feedback on the selection of content:

One respondent said that, given that a data steward has a broad overview of RDM and can provide training, the topic DMP should definitely be included in the training material. The module provides a good overview of what a DMP can help with and how to approach it in order to be able to advise others. Git was not considered as very important.

Recommendation of self-learning modules in training programme for RDM multipliers:

Self-learning modules are not suitable for all levels of knowledge. One expert pointed out that in the RDM context, individual topics and facts can be learned via self-learning. However, in order to become confident enough to advise others in the RDM field, it is necessary for trainers to exchange experiences with others. The topic of the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) was mentioned as an example, for which it is sometimes required to exchange with others on their experience in practice.

The experts recommended designing self-learning material with a clear structure, making the material easy to understand and that it should help engage people in their work. For both, the mixture of face-to-face and self-learning was necessary. One expert advised going for a blended learning approach, i.e. to start with face-to-face sessions, followed by online courses. The other expert also suggested combining face-to-face learning and self-learning in order to receive feedback. The provisioned Rocket.Chat-Channel was mentioned as a communication channel, but one expert pointed out that this was different from having an appointment where learners can ask questions. One respondent stated the time factor, taking into account that participants are also multipliers and have other jobs to perform alongside the course.

Conclusion of the expert interview on self-learning materials:

Both experts stated that self-learning material should be easy to grasp, designed in line with the target group and the learning objectives to be achieved. It is important to both experts that the material varies in formats – video, text, audio, exercises, etc. – and that there are changes between theory and practice, in alignment with Pan et al. (2024). In addition to self-learning, both consider the exchange of experiences in-person or online with others to be necessary so that learners can obtain feedback on their work or ask questions when they get stuck. Self-learning modules are suitable for imparting facts or acquiring knowledge on a specific subject. The topic DMP should be included in the self-learning training material for RDM multipliers. Both experts highlighted this specific module in the RDMTraining4NFDI-provided self-learning material as very well prepared from a didactic point of view and suitable for self-learning. Tool-related topics for beginners should be considered to be taught in live sessions.

Semi-structured interviews with participants of the hybrid event

Feedback on learning formats, the role of trainers and the didactic design of the training event:

At the outset, all participants rated the face-to-face event as the most effective format. They found this type of event particularly motivating, partly because of the personal contact with the trainers and other participants. Learning success was also greatest at the face-to-face event, indicating a direct link between motivation and willingness to learn. One participant also noted that distractions are more likely to occur in online formats, for example due to emails, suggesting that concentration is better onsite and has a positive impact on learning success. Another advantage is that participants onsite can also better benefit from the experiences and challenges of others. In addition, it was emphasised that interaction with trainers is different in face-to-face settings and that content is best conveyed at the same didactic level in live events.

Overall, feedback on the online workshops was mixed. While one participant rated the online formats as generally well implemented, including in terms of technical implementation and trainers, the other two participants were not entirely convinced. One participant criticised the Carpentries-based modules for their lack of focus on the sustainability of learning success: Although instructions were provided, what had been learned was quickly forgotten. It was also noted that greater consortium-specific adaptation of the modules could increase motivation. The didactics workshop and the modules on Python, Galaxy and Git were perceived as particularly conducive to learning. However, opinions on the latter two modules (Galaxy and Git) differed significantly among participants. One respondent reported the greatest learning success due to the highly hands-on nature of the modules, noted that a second part would be desirable to continue the learning process, and observed no significant difference compared to a live workshop. In contrast, another respondent found the modules too easy to work through. This carries the risk of reducing attention and encouraging distractions. One positive aspect highlighted was that almost all participants kept their cameras on during the workshops, which helped strengthen the sense of group cohesion. The use of the companion event pad was also perceived as useful. Possible technical problems, such as unstable internet connections or malfunctioning technology, were cited as disadvantages of online formats, which is why appropriate testing in advance was recommended. In practice-oriented workshops, it can also be challenging when technical difficulties experienced by individual participants interfere with the process.

Feedback on the self-learning modules was also mixed. While some modules were well received, others were not convincing. In the case of one specific module, it was noted that the PDF files were very extensive and the presentation did not give the impression that it was designed for self-learning. This suggests that the preparation of the materials has a significant impact on the learning experience. It was recommended that the self-learning modules be supplemented with exercises to reinforce learning, in alignment with Pan et al. (2024). This approach is in line with the approach taken by another participant, who provides self-learning units after conducting workshops themselves and then reviews the knowledge acquired in a smaller workshop.

One participant rated the homework assignments as very short, for example on the topics of 'open access' and 'open data'. In general, the feedback on the asynchronous homework was very brief. This brief feedback could be due to the fact that the asynchronous homework were most often neglected due to time constraints.

The feedback on the trainers in the face-to-face and online events was consistently positive. Overall, they were perceived as professionally competent and of a high standard. All trainers demonstrated expertise in their respective fields and conveyed the content in a didactically convincing manner. They were able to actively engage the participants, motivate them to engage with the topics, encourage them to think critically and promote exchange among the participants, for example through brief inputs or working on tasks in small groups. It was also emphasised that the motivation of the participants depends heavily on the respective trainers. The selection of trainers therefore has a significant influence on the learning experience and learning success, which aligns with the findings of Zheng (2021) and García et al. (2023).

Since all interviewees are also responsible for organising and/or conducting training courses themselves, they were also asked which format they prefer for training courses they conduct themselves. Here, too, it became apparent that participants prefer face-to-face events, even if this depends in part on the target group and the scope. If a decision is made against a

face-to-face event, this is due to time or logistical reasons. One of the respondents also mentioned that they combine different formats by giving a workshop, preferably face-to-face, then providing self-learning units and finally testing the learning success in a second mini-workshop. The module on DMP, which was designed specially for this event and audience, was very well received, and one of the participants plans to incorporate this topic into future training courses for a deeper understanding.

Insights for the future design of training events and participant-related challenges:

One of the respondents stated that the hybrid format could, in principle, be a viable concept. At the same time, however, it should be ensured that both the expectations of the participants and the overall concept of the event are clearly communicated, for example, with regard to how the various formats are coordinated. One participant reported that this was not entirely clear. Another respondent rated the concept presented in the companion event pad as clear. The reminders via email and the channel Rocket.Chat were highlighted positively. There were also some organisational criticisms from participants. For example, the asynchronous homework should have been announced earlier so that more time could be set aside for it, and the open consultation hour for questions was inconvenient for one person. The latter point would argue in favour of an online exchange group (see below for more details).

The biggest challenge for participants in the training event was the time factor. Respondents reported that, due to time constraints or scheduling conflicts, they were sometimes unable to complete all formats or could only complete them incompletely. This was particularly evident in the asynchronous homework format, which was therefore partially neglected. Motivation also plays a role in completing tasks and participating in the formats. One participant pointed out that the workshop Foundations of RDM is not one of their favorite topics.

As a supplement to the existing concept, an exchange group was mentioned that would also be available after the event had ended. For example, an exchange every three months was suggested in order to clarify any open questions that might arise afterwards or to obtain support. The fact that there were beginner and advanced courses was highlighted as a positive aspect, as it meant that those who already had a certain level of competence in the respective subject did not have to work through the basics again. However, it would have been useful if these modules could be offered several times so that participants could choose between beginner and advanced courses. In addition, it was requested that more time be allocated to certain topics in order to cover them in greater depth.

Professional, social and personal conclusions for participants:

As the participants come from consortia with different scientific disciplines and organise or conduct training courses themselves, they were asked which formats or modules would be suitable for discipline-specific adaptation.

In general, the concept of the training event and the various formats should be clearly defined and structured so that the content can be adapted by the trainers to specific disciplines. While the 'Strategic Data Stewardship and Change Management' course can be used unchanged within the consortia, other, more subject-specific data sets could be used in the Python course without having to change the basic course structure. The course on Practical Data Protection in Research requires the most adaptation due to the processing of personal data. Adaptation would also be easy for the topic of open access; here, only

supplementary information would need to be provided. In addition, it was emphasised that the self-learning modules offered would generally be well suited for adaptation in the various consortia.

The social interaction with other participants during the training event was highlighted as particularly positive. Regardless of the training format, both the group dynamics and the collaborative work were described as very good and positive. In particular, the face-to-face event at the beginning was perceived by the respondents as valuable for social interaction. On the one hand, the content taught is more memorable when working with other people. On the other hand, exchanging experiences with other participants provides valuable learning opportunities. It is also reassuring to realise that other participants, regardless of their level of experience in RDM, are faced with similar challenges and questions.

With regard to the online events, it was suggested that there could be more interaction in the form of group work (e.g. breakout rooms) to promote collaboration and communication, and that the time frame for interaction should be extended. For the online teaching module, the companion event pad was considered a good and useful alternative for social interaction, but it was noted that this was no substitute for a live discussion. This once again underlines the importance of face-to-face social contact. One of the participants stated that the dropout rate for the self-learning modules could possibly be reduced by offering topic-related consultation hours, which once again underlines the central role of the social component in a learning environment.

One of the respondents also stated that they found the exchange with others enriching and felt more confident in their position thanks to the insights gained into the experiences and challenges of other participants within their own consortium. By participating in the training event, this person quickly achieved a level of competence that enabled them to actively participate in and contribute to RDM within the consortium and at their institution.

Asynchronous homework

Participants (n = 2) spent approximately 4-5 hours on the "Asynchronous Homework", noting that a deeper dive into all slides would require significantly more time. While one participant found the quick guide⁹ clear, they felt constrained by the time available. Another participant initially underestimated the task's scope, realising it was much larger than expected, but found the provided presentation and documents helpful for structuring their thoughts.

The format was motivating for one, particularly due to the relevance of the material for future consultations and for colleagues within their institution. One participant, coming from a different field, learned a lot for themselves, especially regarding didactics rather than just data lifecycle. However, maintaining high motivation was difficult for another due to parallel tasks and tight deadlines, especially when encountering already familiar content. The time frame was identified as a significant hurdle, with participants suggesting more time would be beneficial for increased learning.

Participants indicated they would use parts of the material for training, adapting specific slides for their own presentations rather than using the entire package.

⁹ Vandendorpe, J., Manske, A., Wohltmann, M., & Uebachs, M. (2026). From Learning to Practice — Tailoring RDM Training Materials to Your Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18935544>

Regarding technical aspects, publishing materials as editable PowerPoint (.pp) files was preferred over PDFs, and .odp (LibreOffice) was suggested for broader accessibility. The importance of data protection was highlighted, with one participant noting the difficulty of discipline-specific adaptation without specific disciplinary expertise or a dedicated person within consortia. Collaboration was suggested as a way to address the lack of such expertise. The absence of a German version of the slides was also raised as a language barrier.

Focus group discussion

Evaluating the effectiveness of the different formats in the hybrid event is considered feasible by the participants of the focus group discussion (n = 4), though challenging with a small group, and would ideally involve pre- and post-tests or a larger participant pool. Participants generally found the hybrid format, combining an initial in-person meeting with subsequent online modules, to be effective for group building and learning, despite some finding online sessions less profitable than in-person ones. A “big jump” was perceived between the live session and self-learning, and there was a lack of transparency regarding the overall concept and the clear connection between the different formats. Suggestions for improvement included making a “red thread” or storytelling approach for future iterations. The “asynchronous homework” module was identified as potentially less motivating due to its self-directed nature, contrasting with the more focused environment of workshops. However, the social aspect of homework, particularly the “wrap-up” sessions where participants presented their work, was seen as a positive motivator and facilitated discussion across disciplines. To create new discipline-specific materials, participants highlighted the need for time and access to expertise, suggesting collaboration across different disciplines to share knowledge and reduce individual workload. For adapting materials for discipline-specific topics, participants emphasised the need to consider the target group, as different formats (e.g., classical presentations for researchers) would be more suitable.

Rocket.Chat as a communication tool received mixed feedback: while the idea of a messenger was good, some found it overwhelming due to multiple channels and information overload, preferring email for essential information. A dedicated learning platform that integrates materials and communication was suggested as a more effective solution.

Discussion

Challenges faced during the coordination/organisation of the hybrid event

One of the main challenges was the tight timeframe of the project: organising such a large-scale event within a single year required careful prioritisation and planning. As a result, the training was scheduled toward the end of the project, allowing sufficient time for conceptualisation and coordination.

A second challenge concerned identifying a suitable in-person format for our target audience, who are professionals with significant work and family commitments that make attending a full week of in-person training difficult. Additionally, since the COVID-19 pandemic, we have noticed that it is challenging to attract participants to in-person events, although, as demonstrated in this report, they appear to find in-person events more

motivating than online ones. To address this, we opted for a short, lunch-to-lunch in-person kick-off followed exclusively by online sessions of limited duration. This structure made participation more manageable and inclusive, enabling a greater number of people to take part while still giving the possibility to create a learning community with personal connections.

Recruitment also posed a challenge initially due to the limited time of promoting before the start of this event. When participation was limited to our use cases, it proved difficult to attract motivated participants, as some felt obliged to join and ultimately chose not to. Expanding the invitation to second-phase consortia and the wider NFDI community significantly improved engagement and helped us reach a more genuinely interested audience. Providing travel funds for the onsite event was helpful to reach a variety of RDM multipliers.

While finding trainers was relatively straightforward, one potential contributor had to be declined because they were unwilling to share their materials under open access conditions, which conflicted with the project's principles.

Finally, unlike training materials for live sessions, such as slides, we struggled to find reusable training materials for the self-learning modules. This suggests a lack of reusable self-learning materials.

Overall, although the event was large and complex to organise, the integrated format allowed us to combine multiple objectives into a single coherent programme. With more time, separating the components might have been easier, but under the given constraints, the chosen structure proved effective.

Challenges and limitations on the evaluation

Overall, it was challenging to find a suitable approach to evaluate different components (content, satisfaction level, knowledge and effectiveness of format) with different workshop topics, varied participants and trainers, since for example the trainer have influence on the perceived training (Zheng, 2021; García et al., 2023).

We conducted several approaches to gain a broad insight from the participants.

We acknowledge that the number of participants in the survey was low (between 3-10 n for the onsite and online modules) and should bear in mind when reading the results. Similarly, the method is limited in its ability to measure deep knowledge and skills in the results of the pre- and post-tests regarding the Python workshop. We recommend that the RDM community share further training evaluation results and insights to enhance RDM training and gain more insight into the effectiveness of formats and satisfaction levels in RDM training for RDM multipliers.

Recommendations

Must-Have

- For the target group of RDM multipliers, flexibility of training is recommended to suit their calendar.
- We recommend shorter, modular workshops for RDM to increase flexibility and avoid communication overload. If a larger event is planned, we recommend expanding the time frame for a training event.

- For the self-learning modules, clear learning outcomes should be defined in alignment with previous research (Lu et al., 2022). To identify relevant outcomes, we recommend using the *Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement* (Petersen et al., 2025). Further, for an example we recommend using the didactic approach of the DMP module (e.g. by adding reflection & transfer questions to reading activities) when developing self-learning materials.
- Asynchronous homework assignment with a guide¹⁰ could be an option to increase the development of discipline-specific RDM training materials. It is recommended that the offer has a broad range of topics or is tailored to the target group. We recommend that the guide for developing discipline-specific content should be used in collaboration with RDM multipliers within the consortium to encourage stronger collaboration and social learning.

Nice to have

- For the onsite training, it is recommended that travel funds for RDM multipliers be considered in project and budget planning where possible, as this can help enable participation.
- A blended approach to training, beginning with a unified introductory session followed by division into breakout groups based on pre-existing knowledge levels, appears to be an effective methodology.
- It is recommended that self-learning is framed within a live session before and after the self-learning module, in alignment with research (Ren, 2023).
- Open Hours should have a frame of specific topics and the date and time should be varied to increase the likelihood of attendance.
- It is recommended that the entire concept, along with detailed information on a large-scale training event, is made available before the event starts for the target group of RDM multipliers.

Details

- During the online session, it is recommended that participants are reminded to turn off their email client or other tools to reduce distractions.
- A collaborative pad can be used in online sessions as an alternative to breakout sessions.
- In online workshops, breakout sessions are recommended to increase participants' engagement and to foster social learning and community building in the RDM community.

Conclusion

Onsite RDM training for the targeted RDM multipliers is the preferred option and demonstrates the highest level of motivation among participants, while also facilitating networking and professional exchange. We recommend incorporating onsite RDM training

¹⁰ Vandendorpe, J., Manske, A., Wohltmann, M., & Uebachs, M. (2026). From Learning to Practice — Tailoring RDM Training Materials to Your Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18935544>

into training programmes for RDM multipliers. Online workshops should be flexible and offered modularly with interactive tools such as hands-on training, collaborative pads and breakout sessions. There is no clear preference for a preferred tool in the target group.

Methods without live sessions, such as the self-learning module and guide, showed the lowest participation in the target group, mainly due to time constraints and self-organisation. For this format, a broader time frame and well-prepared training in terms of design and didact are recommended. Furthermore, we struggled to identify reusable training materials for the self-learning modules. This suggests a lack of reusable self-learning materials that should be addressed.

The suitability of training materials tested in the format, as noted in this section survey results, varies between topics and different items. We recommend, if RDM multipliers plan to reuse the tested training materials of the RDMTraining4NFDI hybrid event, to consider the insights of this evaluation report. We aim to incorporate insights for adapting the RDM training materials and to provide flexible, modular training in the future.

Outlook

We conclude that, for the Integration phase of RDMTraining4NFDI, we will focus on onsite training and online workshops to foster social learning and motivation, since these seem to be the most effective and satisfying formats for RDM multipliers.

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Author Contributions

J.V. organized and managed the Training Event with support from M.W., R.M., Sina Bock, Marco Uebachs and Alicia Mührenberg, M.W. created the survey and interview questions with support of J.V. and Base4NFDI, M.W. conducted the semi-structured interviews and experts interview with support of Base4NFDI, M.W. conducted the surveys, M.W. and J.V. conducted the focus group discussion, M.W. performed the analysis of the semi-structured interview with support of Base4NFDI, M.W. prepared the analysis plan of the survey data, R.M. performed the analysis of the survey, R.M. and M.W. designed the figures and tables, J.V. wrote the background and the section “Challenges faced during the coordination/organisation of the hybrid event” in the report; M.W. wrote the other parts of the report with support from J.V. in the section “Recommendations” and with support from Base4NFDI for the sections experts interview and semi-structured interviews. All authors commented on the report.

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